

DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM AUTHORITY IN UZBEKISTAN.

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Abstract: Uzbekistan is attracting the attention of the whole world with its many historical and architectural monuments, diverse climate and rapid development. In this article, the development of tourism potential of our country, the beauty of historical cities, nature Information about the charm is given.

Key words: Great Silk Road, exotic country, architectural monuments, science, culture, art, "Mirror of the World".

Over the centuries, Uzbekistan was located on the path of trade, merchants and travelers, geographers and missionaries, invaders and conquerors of the Great Silk Road. At the moment, Uzbekistan is becoming one of the fascinating tourist destinations for those interested in culture, history, tradition and exotic countries. The Ichan-Qala complex in Khiva, historical centers in Bukhara, Shahrisabz and Samarkand cities are included in the special list of UNESCO's "World Heritage". Unique monuments and architectural structures in these cities reflect the past and play a major role in the country's history. Let's get to know these beautiful cities!

Tashkent is the capital of Uzbekistan and one of the largest cities in Central Asia. In the distant past, as well as at present, Tashkent is the crossroads of international transport routes with the help of our own Uzbekistan Airways and international airlines.

Tashkent is one of the oldest cities in the world. In 2009, it celebrated its 2200th anniversary. At the same time, Tashkent is a modern production center, where more than 500 companies produce various products; manufactures everything from airplanes to tractors, from televisions to textiles and shoes. Tashkent is rapidly becoming a modern, developed international metropolis in the harmony of historical monuments and modern skyscrapers.

Today, there are about a hundred museums in Uzbekistan, and half of them are located in the capital of the country. Each of them reflects the rich cultural heritage of the Uzbek people. The State Museum of the History of the Timurids is located in the center of the capital, and its huge blue dome reminds of the ancient dome of Samarkand. Its exhibits testify to the formation of medieval forms of statehood in the territory of Uzbekistan and reflect the development of science, culture and art during the time of Amir Temur.

Samarkand

Over the centuries, the cities of Uzbekistan played an important role in the life of the Great Silk Road and the ancient transcontinental highway. Only Samarkand was named "Heart of the Great Silk Road".

In ancient times, Samarkand was described by names such as "Pearl of Islamic architecture" and "Mirror of the world". Samarkand, whose antiquity is equal to Rome, Athens and Babylon, celebrated its 2750th anniversary. Samarkand reached its highest point of prosperity when it was chosen as the capital of the Great Movarunnahr state during the reign of Amir Temur, the great commander and ruler of Central Asia after Genghis Khan. At this time, extensive urban development works were carried out. The great ruler gathered the most skilled craftsmen and masters of his time in Samarkand, and their works have been alive for centuries. Amir Temur's grandson Ulugbek continued these traditions. Today, the monuments in Samarkand are beautiful and huge. In this city, one can feel the breath of ancient history preserved in ancient ruins, madrasas, mausoleums and minarets. The legendary Registan Square is a unique architectural monument of Central Asia. In ancient times, this square was the commercial and social center of Samarkand. Three huge buildings of Ulugbek, Sherdar and Tillaqori madrasas have been erected here. The Gori-Amir mausoleum is another gem of ancient Samarkand. The graves of the ruler of the great state Amir Temur and his two grandsons, including the great scientist and thinker of the East, Mirzo Ulugbek, are located. The Gori-Amir mausoleum, which looks like a bud, with the leaves of Havarang tulips tightly arranged, is a very famous place for tourists. and several monuments continue to fascinate visitors to the city.

Bukhara

Bukhara has been a densely populated center of the oasis since ancient times. He is 2500 years old. Bukhara, which has preserved more than 140 ancient architectural monuments and a comfortable atmosphere, remains one of the favorite places of tourists.

The mausoleum of Ismail Samoni covered with a net, the huge fortress and the strong residence of the ruler of Bukhara, the Ark, Minarai Kalon, many mosques and madrasahs like a living labyrinth, caravansary palaces, and monuments such as baths are among the incomparable jewels of holy Bukhara. remains.

Khiva

Khiva is a completely preserved city from the era of the Great Silk Road. It is called "open-air museum". The Ichan-Kala complex in the center of the city, where many architectural monuments are located, belongs to the end of the

18th century and the first half of the 19th century. Due to its location at the crossroads of the Great Silk Road and the caravan route passing through it, Ichan-Qala has four gates facing the four directions of the world. The height of the castle wall gives the city a charming look, just like in a real oriental fairy tale. The towers are said to reach the sky, and among them the tallest tower in Uzbekistan is Islam-Khoja. The bright blue domes of mausoleums and mosques stand majestically over the flat roofs of houses. Several of Khiva's khan's palaces have been preserved, the most famous of which is the huge Stone-Court Palace, where ceremonies are held, where the khan rests and the khan's harems live. The exterior and walls are covered with mosaic-decorated stones. One day is not enough to know the beauty of the city, to explore its narrow streets and to feel the true taste of the "open-air museum".

Termez

The multifaceted history of Uzbekistan undoubtedly reflects its geographical location. Termiz is the southernmost city of the country. Termiz was founded on the caravan route on the right side of the Amudarya coast and has been serving as the main port for 2500 years. At the beginning of our era, Termiz was the main center of Buddhism in Central Asia. The stone-carved Buddhist monastery at Kara-Tepa, the Buddhist temple at Fayoz-Tepa, and the remains of many limestone Buddha statues are famous places for tourists and Buddhist worshipers. Termiz is not only famous for its Buddhist monuments. There are also a number of interesting historical monuments from the beginning of the Middle Ages. Among them are the tomb of Hakim al-Tirmizi, the ensemble of Sultan Saadat (10th-17th centuries) and the legendary Kirq-Kiz fortress (9th century).

Karakalpakstan

Today, Karakalpakstan is a living link between the present and the ancient past. This place is ready to share its legends and secrets with interesting and unique places, unexpected findings and discoveries.

Kirq-Kiz, Ayozi-Kala, Janbus-Kala, Ishan-Kala mausoleum, the unique Tuproq-Kala and other historical monuments located in Karakalpakstan arouse scientific and cultural interest and attract local and foreign tourists.

Although the field of tourism in Uzbekistan is relatively new, it has been ahead of many other fields in development. Our country has a great potential for the development of international tourism. Twenty years ago, no one knew Uzbekistan as a promising tourism region. After gaining independence, the state developed new principles in the field of tourism. On July 27, 1992, the national

company "Uzbekturizm" was established by the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The main task of "Uzbektourism" is to implement state policy in the field of tourism and create a national model of tourism development.

In addition, the national company coordinates the activities of all tourist organizations in the republic, encourages the development of all directions of tourism, deals with personnel issues, attracts investment flows to the formation of the material and technical base and the development of industry infrastructure. Since 1993, our country has been "International is a member of the Tourism Organization (UNWTO). Since 2004, in Samarkand - the "heart" of the great Silk Road, the office of UNWTO, which is engaged in the coordination of tourism on the transcontinental highway, has been operating.

The government is doing great work in the fields of modernization of the tourism industry, improvement of transport and hotel infrastructure in the state, and improvement of the regulatory legal framework in tourism.

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